

The Role of Spiritual Leadership in Reducing Workplace Anxiety: A Study on the Industrial Companies in Egypt

Author Details: Wageeh A. Nafei-
University of Sadat City, Menoufia, Egypt

Abstract

The objective of the research is to identify the role of Spiritual Leadership (SL) in controlling Workplace Anxiety (WA) at the industrial companies in Egypt. The research community consists of all the employees at the industrial companies (the iron and steel sector, the construction sector, the food industry, the spinning and weaving sector and the chemical industries sector) in Sadat city in Egypt. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted a sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results; the most important of which are: (1) the availability of some administrative factors that cause WA such as the lack of welcome of the senior management of the organization to the idea of Telework, and the failure to recruit employees in the degree of career commensurate with their experience and skills, and the existence of a capacity of competition between the administrative departments of the organization in a manner that causes problems to each other, senior management to criticize and blame the workers, In addition to ignoring some in the promotion movement within the organization. This is in addition to the existence of a set of individual factors that cause WA such as the inability of the individual to achieve a balance between duties and social responsibilities, resulting in a sense of mental fatigue, and delay the performance of some of the tasks to be accomplished. In addition, the employee loses the ability to develop his career. This is reflected in his belief that the introduction of the computer threatens his job stability and that the training courses are a waste of time, and (2) there is a statistically significant inverse correlation between the variable of SL and the variable of WA where the greater the interest in SL, the less WA is at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

The study referred to a number of recommendations; the most important of which are: (1) the degree of WA varies in terms of their nature and degree of impact on employees. It may be an impetus for development and improvement, an opportunity for challenge and self-validation, and may be a source of innovation and the emergence of creative ideas. Therefore, it is important to consider the factors that lead to increased willingness and willingness of the employees to express their ideas and opinions and to enhance their positive attitudes towards the process of innovation and creativity by providing material and moral incentives to motivate them to innovate and innovate, (2) conduct positive training courses and focus on the need to provide senior management support to staff members in a manner that prevents WA. Training courses are a means of building positive skills, abilities and behaviors, not a waste of time, (3) taking into account the appointment of employees in the appropriate degree of expertise, skills and abilities, (4) adopting modern administrative methods in work, such as Telework, which ensures the possibility of continuous communication of employees with their organization regardless of their social conditions in different forms, (5) rehabilitation training courses that support the change of individual factors that cause resistance to change, (6) to confirm the employee's ability to self-development by converting him to the conviction that the introduction of the computer does not threaten his career stability, but saves his time, and raises the degree of quality and accuracy of work.

1. Introduction

There are new concepts in the contemporary administrative business environment, the most important being Spiritual Leadership (SL) (Fry, 2003; Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is very popular in education, health care and psychology as well as in management research. There has been an increase in the number of studies carried out, showing interest in SL (Klaus & Fernando, 2016).

SL will play an important role in improving the level of organizational commitment on the one hand and productivity on the other. In addition to their positive impact on the individual, the difference, the construction of organizational values, and the sense of society (Jerry, 2009; Chen & Li, 2013).

SL will belong to a transformational leadership school, focusing on behavior, messages about vision, ambition, emotional feelings, ideological and moral values, attention to individuals, the intellectual motivation of the leader and subordinates (Chen & Li, 2013).

SL plays an important role in creating a positive work environment, new working relationships, and motivating subordinates in a way that contributes to the organization's goals efficiently and effectively (Polat, 2011).

The concept of Workplace Anxiety (WA) is particularly relevant during organizational change, when both organizations and individuals within them are under stress (Cooper et al., 2002).

The danger of WA is its negative effects, the most prominent of which is the state of psychological combustion. The phenomenon of psychological combustion has become one of the general phenomena that have become widespread and have increased in recent times (Sweeny & McFarlane, 2002).

The causes of WA are unclear objectives, organizational unemployment, routine, uncertainty, misperception, complex issues (Paul & Anderson, 2007).

Anxiety and depressive disorders have been found to be among the most commonly diagnosed mental disorders, affecting millions of people in many of their daily aspects of life (Mucci et al., 2016). About one-third of the general population suffers from mental disorders (Wittchen, et al., 2011).

Anxiety, as a human phenomenon, has attracted the interest and attention of a wide range of researchers, and thus has been perceived differently by various researchers. Generally speaking, anxiety is defined a feeling of excessive worry and concern (fearful expectations) over one's future (Abdul'Aal, 2008).

Worry is closely related to anxiety. Worry is the attention vigilance and distortion in information processing, such as attention and encoding, which characterizes anxiety. Basically, worry is the cognitive component of anxiety and it represents a functional state of preparation for future threats through lessening the unexpectedness and consequent impact of aversive stimuli (Barlow, 1988; 2004).

Worry decreases the surprise element and increases the individual's readiness for coping with unanticipated events that actually occur by (a) alarming the system about new incoming threatening information; (b) prompting retrieval of threat-related images and thoughts into consciousness; and (c) preparing for a future situation in a way that reduces its aversiveness (Levy, 2005; Spector, 2008).

The current study seeks to determine the role of SL (vision, hope/faith, altruism, meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, productivity) in controlling WA (lack of incentives for Telework, negative management outlook for employees, increase organizational conflicts, the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social, loss of ability to develop career) at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

2. Spiritual Leadership

2.1. Spiritual Leadership Concept

SL is highly popular in education, health care, psychology, as well as in management research. There has been an increase in the number of studies carried out, which shows the interest in SL (Kluas & Fernando, 2016).

SL is the use of the leader of his spiritual side as one of the motivational behaviors of his subordinates in a way that helps them discover the moral strength that binds them to others (Lean, 2012).

A number of researchers in social research, in general, and administrative research, in particular, have been interested in SL (Giacalone and Jurkiewicz, 2003).

SL is one of the types of leadership that seeks to satisfy the needs and desires of the employees in the organization by providing psychological needs that help them to continue working in the organization and communicate with others, and belonging to the organization in a way that leads to efficiency in the performance of business, (Chun et al., 2012).

SL is one of the methods that can be followed to improve organizational performance through leaders' attitudes that motivate employees to achieve the goals and vision of their organization (Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is one of the forms of leadership that can be followed by leaders in an organization in a way that achieves its goals efficiently and effectively (Karadag, 2009).

SL is a set of human values that constitute the working environment of an organization, where its employees demonstrate their abilities and skills (Burkhart, 2008).

SL is a set of aspects relating to the personality of the individual, which serves as the primary engine of the physical body (Wilson et al., 2008).

SL is a set of positive emotions such as gratitude, forgiveness, and hope that have proven to help individuals engage in behaviors that contribute to productivity and the development of relationships within the organization (Bono & McCullough, 2006).

SL is a form of leadership and seeks to transform the workplace into a more comfortable and productive place, on the one hand, and providing the needs of employers and employees on the other (Thankappan, 2005).

SL is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to motivate one's self, on the one hand, and to motivate others on the other (Fry, 2003).

SL is a reliable leadership technique in motivating subordinates to achieve high levels of organizational and productive commitment. It is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors that stimulate one's self and others in order to have a sense of survival in a spiritual life (Fry et al., 2005).

SL is a phenomenon that occurs in the organization when the leader is honest and modest in his actions, and behavior in the organization in a way that reflects his respect for himself and others. It is one of the forms of leadership that can be used to provide the basic needs of employees, on the one hand, and to achieve satisfaction on the other. This is in addition to changing the business philosophy towards the organization from being mutually beneficial with the organization that they are working to achieve their own values (Reave, 2005).

SL is one of the methods of integrating the values, processes and systems of the organization with the values and aspirations of its personnel, in other words creating an atmosphere of harmony between individuals and the organization (Benefiel, 2005).

SL is to teach subordinates the methods that enable them to govern themselves and create the right conditions so subordinates can work freely with their leaders within the organization (Fairholm, 1996).

2.2. Spiritual Leadership Dimensions

There are six dimensions of SL (Polat, 2011). They can be explained as follows:

1. Vision

There must be a clear vision of what the organization would like to be in the future. The term vision was rarely used in leadership literature until the 1980s. At the moment, leaders in business organizations have had to give greater attention to future direction due to the intensity of competition and technological development. Spiritual leaders try to motivate subordinates through a clear vision of the organization.

2. Hope / Faith

Hope is the desire to expect achievement; faith is beyond hope or expectation of something desirable; faith is more than just a wish for something. It depends on values, attitudes and behaviors that ensure certainty and absolute certainty that what is desired and expected will be achieved. In general, hope and faith are the sources of belief and conviction that the vision and mission of the Organization will be realized.

3. Altruistic Love

Altruistic love is the sense of integration, harmony, and well-being resulting from the care, attention and appreciation of both self and others. This concept; also, includes the values of patience, compassion, tolerance, humility, altruism, trust, loyalty, and sincerity. In addition, the altruistic love in the SL helps to get rid of destructive feelings such as fear, anger, feeling of failure and others.

4. Meaning/significance of work

The concept of meaning refers to whether members of the organization believe that the functions they perform are significant and meaningful, and by engaging in work, individuals derive meaning and purpose from life. In addition, individuals who have an internal motivation and drive to learn are finding work, as well as individuals who want to be members of the work group feel they have value and contribution to performance. It is; therefore, clear that meaning and sense of importance are associated with spirituality in the workplace.

5. Membership

Most individuals tend to work in a group or team, and they prefer to work in an environment in which leaders appreciate their contributions to achieving their goals. Leaders must therefore be able to create a culture that involves leaders and subordinates interested and responsible for themselves and others. This culture must create a sense of membership. SL must therefore take care of the employees in such a way as to create an atmosphere of friendliness and trust among all staff of the organization.

6. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is one of the main axes of organizational success. SL plays an important role in influencing the level of organizational commitment. The appropriate leadership styles lead to increased level of job satisfaction for employees. SL also plays an important role in achieving organizational identification and organizational loyalty through organizational commitment and the desire to remain and work in the organization.

7. Productivity

The availability of the element of hope / faith in the vision of the Organization, their sense of importance and membership makes them do their best to carry out activities that achieve the vision of the Organization and thereby increase productivity. It should be noted that SL plays an important role in increasing the level of job satisfaction, which in turn leads to increased productivity in the organization.

3. Workplace Anxiety

3.1. Workplace Anxiety Concept

The term “Anxiety” describes the effect of combined negative affect and physiological arousal. This refers to anxiety as an evolved defense system that has served through eons of time to protect organisms from survival threats (Ohman, 2000).

If the feeling of anxiety continues for a longer period (about over six months) and dominates an individual's thought pattern and mental state, then it can be said that the given individual is beset with general anxiety disorder. This disorder is characterized by the lack of control over thoughts and worries, which in turn result in certain specific somatic and cognitive symptoms, which are likely to interfere with an individual's daily functioning (Davey & Tallis, 1994).

Anxiety is a universal phenomenon, often challenging and beneficial at the same time. It acts as a biological warning system against danger signs and prepares an individual to take appropriate action. Anxiety acts as a protective response towards certain risks. A low level of anxiety is beneficial, but high and chronic levels of anxiety result in impairment of physiological and psychological functions (Noyes & Hoehn-Saric 1998).

An anxious person is unhappy. The greater his concern, the more likely he is to be able to remove the concerns, since in practice, the human being needs some anxiety to work efficiently (Management, 2014).

WA is a psychological condition that occurs when the individual feels that there is a danger that he or she expects to occur or is afraid of, namely emotional tension and mental and physical disorder (Kan et al., 2013).

WA is one of the elements of professional stress that interacts between stimuli and responsiveness to job satisfaction (Lokman et al., 2011).

WA is an unpleasant feeling characterized by fear, dread, and fear that the individual feels at a time and in different degrees (Baruch & Lambert, 2007).

The common symptoms include the presence of extreme fear and anxiety, together with behavioral disturbances. Fear is a spontaneous response towards real or perceived threat of immediate danger. Anxiety, however, is directed towards future danger. The only differences among these disorders are the types of situations inducing fear, anxiety and avoidance behavior with linked cognitive dysfunctional ideation. They are highly comorbid with each other but close examination can differentiate the type of anxiety disorder (National Institute of Mental Health 2016).

According to the American Psychiatric Association (2013), Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders has classified anxiety into following categories;

1. **Separation anxiety disorder:** Characterized by persistent fear and anxiety about separation and the degree is usually inappropriate.
2. **Selective autism:** Characterized by consistent failure to speak only in social circumstances.
3. **Specific phobia:** Characterized by consistent fear and anxiety about specific object or situations.
4. **Social anxiety disorder:** Characterized by being fearful and anxious and avoiding the social circumstances where there is possibility of being embarrassed.
5. **Panic disorder:** Characterized by recurrent panic attacks and persistent concern about having panic attacks or behavioral changes due to panic attacks.
6. **Panic attack specifics:** Characterized by intense fear or discomfort which reaches peak within some minutes.
7. **Agoraphobia:** Characterized by being fearful and anxious about using public transportation; being in open spaces, being in enclosed places; standing in line or with crowd; or being outside of the home alone in other situations.
8. **Generalized anxiety disorder:** Characterized by persistent worry and anxiety about work and performances, which is difficult to control.
9. **Substance/medication-induced anxiety disorder:** Characterized by anxiety due to substance use, withdrawal or medical treatment.
10. **Anxiety disorder due to another medical condition:** Anxiety due to other medical conditions.

In the light of the foregoing, organizational concern is the reactions of an individual as a result of environmental or subjective factors that make him unable to adapt to them; thus reducing his ability to innovate and innovate at work.

3.2. Workplace Anxiety Dimensions

The causes of WA are (1) doing many things and learning new things for the process of change, which entails consuming the energies of the workers and working for several more hours, (2) fear of the unknown, where the results of change are often unknown and unclear, (3) a sense of loss of control over the behaviors of employees during work (Voyer et al., 1997).

The causes of WA are the existence of objective goals, unemployment, routine, uncertainty, and misinterpretation. Organizational concerns include (1) suppressed thoughts, feelings, anomalies, and immoral memories; (2) the attitudes and situations in which the individual is expected to be hated or changed in his life, but he does not know his fate, and this is not known, and (3) Anxiety is caused by the fact that man is a conscious thinker of his existence and his work (Paul & Ederson, 2007).

WA is caused by several factors (1) the inability of the individual to balance functional communication and social communication, (2) the inability to develop career, (3) the lack of incentives for Telework (4) the negative management view of employees (Maruyama & Tietze 2012).

The causes of WA are (1) the intensification of organizational conflicts, (2) the adoption by senior management of workplace bullying (Lokman et al., 2011).

In light of the above, there are two dimensions of WA (Jenkins et al., 2011; Matthiesen & Einarsen, 2007; Nilesen et al., 2008). They can be explained as follows:

1. **Administrative factors** such as lack of incentives for Telework (the organization does not welcome work through the Internet and my responsibilities are to work longer than the time available) negative management outlook for employees (do not underestimate my career and severe attendance and departure from work) increase organizational conflicts (my current work does not interest me, there is a difference between the views of the workers in one section, there is a lack of cooperation with other administrative departments, and other administrative departments create problems for our department) the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work (I charge for work that does not fit my career, insisting on practical criticism, take administrative and legal action against me, pressure on the denial of my rights such as holidays and allowances, formation in my career, I have consistently asked for an achievement rate, difficulty getting the information necessary for my work, my observation and observation are constantly monitored, and the movement of promotions is ignored).
2. **Individual factors** such as the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social (delay in official working hours, my constant feeling of exhaustion, mental exhaustion causes me a lot of trouble in my work, delay the performance of some tasks to be accomplished, and frequent work pressures cause me a state of constant anxiety) loss of ability to develop career (computer entry threatens career stability and training courses are a waste of working time).

4. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable for the study of SL. There is one dependent variable WA. The research model is as shown in the following figure:

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that SL has an impact on WA. SL as measured consisted of vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity (Fry & Matherly, 2006). WA is measured in the terms of lack of incentives for Telework, negative management outlook for employees, increase organizational conflicts, the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social, loss of ability to develop career (Jenkins et al., 2011; Matthiesen & Einarsen, 2007; Nilesen et al., 2008).

5. Research Questions

The researcher reached the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature review that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between SL and WA in the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

In light of the review of previous studies towards SL, literature has shown that there is a significant relationship between SL and organizational commitment, productivity, and satisfaction. SL plays the mediating role in the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and productivity (Fry et al., 2017). SL positively influences the spirituality of the work environment (Afsar et al., 2016). There is also a statistically significant relationship between SL and organizational citizenship behavior (Kaya, 2015).

There is a significant relationship between SL and organizational learning and entrepreneurship (Shafiqhi et al., 2013). Another study points out that there is a relationship between SL and job satisfaction (Masouleh et al., 2013). There is a significant relationship between SL and the behavior of organizational citizenship. In other words, SL leads to increased behavior of organizational citizenship (Chen & Yang, 2012).

The problem of bullying is a serious problem in society. However, there is insufficient attention to this problem in Arab societies, whether in terms of the spread of this problem, or even the diagnostic tools. On the other hand, Western societies have given this problem a great deal of attention in all areas, whether through the media or websites, or awareness campaigns to address this problem (Scarpacia, 2006).

As for WA, literature has shown that there is a study that used Telework as a dimension of WA for less than one year in order to identify the expectations of employees before and after the use of the method of Telework, taking into account demographic factors such as gender, job nature, social status and working hours. The study found that employees have negative attitudes toward Telework before using them. These trends have turned into positive trends after the use of Telework, especially among female employees. This method provides them more time to be able to accomplish their family and functional tasks. As well as sales and marketing staff. The study also found that Telework is an effective way to reduce WA, which is one of the negative aspects of the workplace (Maruyama & Tietze 2012).

The latest survey by the American Association of Anxiety Disorders (ADA) showed how stress and anxiety can be related to the workplace. The results of this survey showed that workplace anxiety can affect workplace performance, employee relationships, quality of work, and relationships with supervisors. Furthermore, the workplace can affect anxiety by pressing deadlines, interpersonal relationships and dealing with issues or problems that may arise during the performance of work activities. With regard to the relationship between anxiety and work, concepts of "workplace anxiety" and "workplace phobia" are emerging as new concepts of clinical work (Muschalla, 2009).

A study aimed at applying change management theory to address WA by identifying the factors of concern that the study divided into individual factors and management factors (Baruch & Lambert 2007).

The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted an interview with (30) employees at the industrial companies in Egypt to identify the dimensions of SL and WA. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the blurred important and vital role that could be played by SL in controlling WA at the industrial companies in Egypt. The research questions of this study are as follows:

Q1: What is the relationship between SL (vision) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between (Hope/Faith) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q4: What are the nature and the extent of the relationship between SL (Meaning/Calling) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q5: What is the relationship between SL (Membership) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q6: What is the nature of the relationship between (Organizational commitment) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

Q7: What is the extent of the relationship between SL (Productivity) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt?

6. Research Hypotheses

In the light of the review of previous studies towards SL, the literature has shown that SL has a significant impact on the spirituality of the work environment. SL has no significant impact on job satisfaction. The spirituality of the work environment has a significant impact on job satisfaction. The spirituality of the work environment does not affect the behavior of employees (Sani et al., 2016). In addition, there is a statistically significant relationship between SL and organizational performance. SL also has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance (Salehzadeh et al., 2015). There is also a significant correlation between SL and QWL (Bardmili et al., 2013). There is a positive correlation between SL and the happiness of working individuals (Zavareh et al., 2013). In addition, there is a statistically significant relationship between SL and the empowerment of employees (Esfahani et al., 2013). One of the studies found a positive and statistically significant relationship between SL and organizational outcomes such as organizational commitment and productivity. The study also indicated that spiritual well-being plays an important role as an intermediate variable between SL and organizational outcomes (Fry et al., 2017). Finally, another study indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between SL and organizational culture. The study also pointed out that attendance as one of the dimensions of SL plays an important role in influencing performance, which is reflected in the organizational culture (Karadag, 2009).

As for WA, literature has shown that the awareness of bullying according to his experience of the concept of justice, and to determine the psychological safety of the victim. The study was applied to employees at different administrative levels who had already practiced bullying behavior and to interview a number of bullying. The study found that WA is the result of bullying practices in the workplace, as well as a host of other negative phenomena of frustration, stress, and isolation (Jenkins et al., 2011). Another study found that WA is caused by the individual's inability to balance his relationships between customers and co-workers. The study found that WA for doctors is caused by their inability to balance their relationships between their patients on the one hand and their colleagues on the other (Lokman et al., 2011). In particular, workplace phobia is the most serious workplace concern. It can affect the organization's performance as it relates to absence. In order to deepen the knowledge of this clinical concept, which is not now studied in terms of aspects of the potential work environment, the main objective of this study is to analyze workplace anxiety phobia in the context of the most commonly used model on psychosocial risk factors and stress at work (Demerouti, et al., 2001).

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between SL and WA.

H1: There is no relationship between SL (vision) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

H2: SL (Hope/Faith) has no significant effect on WA at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

H3: There is no relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

H4: SL (Meaning/Calling) has no significant impact on WA at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

H5: There is no relationship between SL (Membership) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

H6: SL (Organizational commitment) has no significant influence on WA at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

H7: There is no relationship between SL (Productivity) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

7. Research Strategy

7.1. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. The total population is 20200 employees. Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 377 employees at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt is presented in the following table.

Table (1): Distribution of the Sample Size

Industrial Companies	Employees	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Iron and Steel Sector	8100	40%	377X 40% = 150
2. Construction Sector	5926	29%	377X 29% = 110
3. Food Industries Sector	2087	10%	377X 10% = 38
4. Textile Sector	2520	13%	377X 13% = 49
5. Chemical Industries Sector	1567	8%	377X 8% = 30
Total	20200	100%	377X 100% = 377

Source: Personnel Department at Industrial Companies, Sadat City, Egypt, 2017

Table (2): Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage	
1- Sex	Male	230	77%
	Female	70	23%
	Total	300	100%
2- Marital Status	Single	130	44%
	Married	170	56%
	Total	300	100%
3- Age	Under 30	100	33%
	From 30 to 45	125	42%
	Above 45	75	25%
	Total	300	100%
4- Educational Level	Secondary school	75	25%
	University	175	58%
	Post Graduate	50	17%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	50	17%
	From 5 to 10	200	67%
	More than 10	50	16%
	Total	300	100%

7.2. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the significant role of SL in controlling WA. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to SL, WA, and biographical information of employees at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. About 377 questionnaires were distributed by employing diverse modes of communication, such as in person and post. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 79%.

7.3. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 35-item scale SL section is based on Fry & Matherly, 2006. There were five items measuring vision, five items measuring hope/faith, seven items measuring altruistic love, four items measuring meaning/significance of work, five items measuring membership, four items measuring commitment, and five items measuring productivity.

The 24-item scale WA section is based on Jenkins et al., 2011; Matthiesen & Einarsen, 2007; Nilesen et al., 2008. There were two items measuring lack of incentives for Telework, two items measuring negative management outlook for employees, four items measuring increase organizational conflicts, nine items measuring the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, five items measuring the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social, and two items measuring loss of ability to develop career.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement which ranges from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

7.4. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (4) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

8. Hypotheses Testing

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics was performed to find out means and standard deviations of SL and WA.

Table (3): shows the mean and standard deviations of SL and WA

Research Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
SL	Vision	3.36	0.635
	Hope/Faith	3.17	0.649
	Altruistic Love	3.03	0.628
	Meaning/Calling	3.36	0.746
	Membership	3.17	0.650
	Organizational Commitment	3.16	0.685
	Productivity	2.84	0.585
	Total Measurement	3.14	0.613
WA	Lack of Incentives for Telework	1.77	0.708
	Negative Management Outlook for Employees	1.73	0.645
	Increase Organizational Conflicts	1.73	0.578
	Senior Management Adopts the Method of Bullying at Work	1.61	0.458
	The Inability of the Individual to Balance the Functional and Social	1.63	0.481
	Loss of Ability to Develop Career	1.87	0.725
		Total Measurement	1.68

According to Table (3), among the various facets of SL, most of the respondents identified the presence of vision ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.635$), hope/faith ($M=3.17$, $SD=0.649$), altruistic love ($M=3.03$, $SD=0.628$), meaning/significance of work ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.746$), membership ($M=3.17$, $SD=0.650$), organizational commitment ($M=3.16$, $SD=0.685$), productivity ($M=2.84$, $SD=0.585$), and total SL ($M=3.14$, $SD=0.613$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of WA (lack of incentives for Telework, negative management outlook for employees, increase organizational conflicts, the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social, loss of ability to develop career). Most of the respondents identified the presence of lack of incentives for Telework ($M=1.77$, $SD=0.708$), negative management outlook for employees ($M=1.73$, $SD=0.645$), increase organizational conflicts ($M=1.73$, $SD=0.578$), the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work ($M=1.61$, $SD=0.458$), the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social ($M=1.63$, $SD=0.481$), loss of ability to develop career ($M=1.87$, $SD=0.725$), and total WA ($M=1.68$, $SD=0.476$).

8.1. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (4): Reliability of SL and WA

Research Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
SL	Vision	5	0.684
	Hope/Faith	5	0.712
	Altruistic Love	7	0.789
	Meaning/Calling	4	0.745
	Membership	5	0.770
	Organizational Commitment	4	0.661
	Productivity	5	0.610
	Total Measurement	35	0.959
WA	Lack of Incentives for Telework	2	0.778
	Negative Management Outlook for Employees	2	0.630
	Increase Organizational Conflicts	4	0.788
	The Senior Management Adopts the Method of Bullying at Work	9	0.838
	The Inability of the Individual to Balance the Functional and Social	5	0.726
	Loss of Ability to Develop Career	2	0.838
	Total Measurement	24	0.943

To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach’s Alpha test was conducted. Table (4) shows the reliability results for SL and WA. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge’s (2004) criteria.

Table (4) presents the reliability of SL. The reliabilities of s vision, hope/faith, altruistic love, meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity are generally higher. The 35 items of SL are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.959. The vision, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.684. The 5 items related to hope/faith, are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.712 while the 7 items of altruistic love are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.789. The meaning/significance of work which consists of 4 items is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.745. The 5 items related to membership are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.770 while the 4 items of organizational commitment are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.661. Productivity which consists of 5 items is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.610. Thus, the internal consistency of SL can be acceptable.

According to Table (4), the 24 items of WA are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.943. The lack of incentives for Telework, which consists of 2 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.778. The 2 items related to negative management outlook for employees are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.630 while the 4 items of increase organizational conflicts are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.788. The senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, which consists of 9 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.838. The 5 items related to inability of the individual to balance the functional and social are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.726 while the 2 items of loss of ability to develop career are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.838. Thus, the internal consistency of WA can be acceptable.

Accordingly, three scales were defined, SL (35 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented about 0.959, and WA (24 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented 0.923.

8.2. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (5): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Research Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	SL	WA
Spiritual Leadership	3.14	0.613	1	
Workplace Anxiety	1.68	0.476	0.414**	1

Table (5) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of significant correlation between variables (SL, and WA). The level of SL of employees is high (Mean=3.14; SD=0.613), while WA is (Mean=1.68; SD=0.476).

8.3. The Correlation between SL and WA

The relationship between SL and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (6): Correlation Matrix between SL and WA

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Vision	1							
Hope/Faith	0.889**	1						
Altruistic Love	0.849**	0.961**	1					
Meaning/Calling	0.865**	0.742**	0.748**	1				
Membership	0.848**	0.960**	0.967**	0.773**	1			
Commitment	0.893**	0.919**	0.910**	0.917**	0.926**	1		
Productivity	0.781**	0.914**	0.970**	0.651**	0.933**	0.820**	1	
WA	0.133**	0.086**	0.057**	0.160**	0.103**	0.135**	0.106**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Based on the Table (6), correlation between SL (vision) and WA is 0.133. For SL (hope/faith) and WA, the value is 0.086 whereas SL (altruistic love) and WA shows correlation value of 0.057. Also, the correlation between SL (meaning/calling) and WA is 0.160. For SL (membership) and WA, the value is 0.103 whereas SL (organizational commitment), and WA shows correlation value of 0.135. Finally, correlation between SL (productivity) and WA is 0.106. The overall correlation between SL and WA is 0.414.

8.4. Spiritual Leadership (Vision) and WA

The relationship between SL (Vision) and WA is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between SL (vision) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

Table (7): MRA Results for SL (Vision) and WA

The Variables of Vision	Beta	R	R ²
1. I understand and am committed to my organization’s vision.	0.244*	0.026	0.001
2. My workgroup has a vision statement that brings out the best in me.	0.779**	0.802	0.643
3. My organization’s vision inspires my best performance.	0.203**	0.119	0.014
4. I have faith in my organization’s vision for its employees.	0.150**	0.053	0.002
5. My organization’s vision is clear and compelling to me.	0.182**	0.103	0.010
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.818 0.669 119.054 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01	* P < .05		

As Table (7) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.818 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of SL (Vision) construe WA significantly.

Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of SL (Vision) can explain 67% of the total factors in WA level.

Hence, 33% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.5. Spiritual Leadership (Hope/Faith) and WA

The relationship between SL (Hope/Faith) and WA is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: SL (Hope/Faith) has no significant effect on WA at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.809. This means that WA has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of SL (Hope/Faith).

As a result of the value of R², the five independent variables of SL (Hope/Faith) justified only 65% of the total factors in WA level.

Hence, 35% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (8) MRA Results for SL (Hope/Faith) and WA

The Variables of Hope/Faith	Beta	R	R ²
1. I have faith in my organization and I am willing to “do whatever it takes” to insure that it accomplishes its mission.	0.109*	0.119	0.014
2. I persevere and exert extra effort to help my organization succeed because I have faith in what it stands for.	0.796**	0.802	0.643
3. I always do my best in my work because I have faith in my organization and its leaders.	0.059	0.126	0.015
4. I set challenging goals for my work because I have faith in my organization and want us to succeed.	0.083	0.051	0.002
5. I demonstrate my faith in my organization and its mission by doing everything I can to help us succeed.	0.052	0.004	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.809 0.654 111.222 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01		* P < .05	

8.6. Spiritual Leadership (Altruistic Love) and WA

The relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and WA is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

Table (9): MRA Results for SL (Altruistic Love) and WA

The Variables of Altruistic Love	Beta	R	R ²
1. My organization really cares about its people.	0.065*	0.053	0.002
2. My organization is kind and considerate toward its employees.	0.796**	0.802	0.643
3. The leaders in my organization “walk the walk” as well as “talk the talk”.	0.144*	0.119	0.014
4. My organization is trustworthy and loyal to its employees.	0.058	0.051	0.002
5. My organization does not punish honest mistakes.	0.133*	0.001	0.001
6. The leaders in my organization are honest and without false pride.	0.024	0.070	0.004
7. The leaders in my organization have the courage to stand up for their people.	0.052	0.126	0.015
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.815 0.664 82.422 7, 292 2.63 0.000	
** P < .01		* P < .05	

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.815 demonstrating that the 7 independent variables of SL (Altruistic Love) construe WA significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 7 independent variables of SL (Altruistic Love) can explain only 68% of the total factors in WA level. Hence, 32% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.7. Spiritual Leadership (Meaning/Calling) and WA

The relationship between SL (Meaning/Calling) and WA is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: SL (Meaning/Calling) has no significant impact on WA at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

Table (10): MRA Results for SL (Meaning/Calling) and WA

The Variables of Meaning/Calling	Beta	R	R ²
1. The work I do is very important to me.	0.092	0.061	0.003
2. My job activities are personally meaningful to me.	0.783**	0.802	0.643
3. The work I do is meaningful to me.	0.266**	0.119	0.014
4. The work I do makes a difference in people's lives.	0.149**	0.053	0.002
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.814	
		0.662	
		144.714	
		4, 295	
		3.31	
		0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.814. This means that WA has been significantly explained by the 4 independent variables of SL (Meaning/Calling).

As a result of the value of R² the 4 independent variables of SL (Meaning/Calling) justified 66% of the total factors in WA level. Hence, 34% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.8. Spiritual Leadership (Membership) and WA

The relationship between SL (Membership) and WA is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

H5: There is no relationship between SL (Membership) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between SL (Membership) and WA in significance level of 0,000.

Moreover, the value of R², the 5 independent variables of SL (Membership) can explain 65% of the total differentiation in WA level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of SL (Membership) and WA is obtained. Because MCC is 0.81, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (11): MRA Results for SL (Membership) and WA

The Variables of Membership	Beta	R	R ²
1. I feel my organization understands my concerns.	0.162**	0.119	0.014
2. I feel my organization appreciates me, and my work.	0.801**	0.802	0.643
3. I feel highly regarded by my leadership.	0.002	0.051	0.002
4. I feel I am valued as a person in my job.	0.001	0.048	0.002
5. I feel my organization demonstrates respect for me, and my work.	0.111	0.070	0.004
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.809	
		0.654	
		111.358	
		5, 294	
		3.01	
		0.000	
** P < .01			

8.9. Spiritual Leadership (Organizational Commitment) and WA

The relationship between SL (Organizational Commitment) and WA is determined. The sixth hypothesis to be tested is:

H6: SL (Organizational commitment) has no significant influence on OP at industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

Table (12): MRA Results for SL (Organizational Commitment) and WA

The Variables of Organizational Commitment	Beta	R	R ²
1. I do not feel like “part of the family” in this organization.	0.139*	0.061	0.003
2. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	0.795**	0.802	0.643
3. I talk up this organization to my friends as a great place to work for.	0.242**	0.119	0.014
4. I really feel as if my organization’s problems are my own.	0.072*	0.052	0.002
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.809 0.655 139.802 4, 295 3.31 0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.81. WA has been significantly explained by the 4 variables of SL (Organizational Commitment). As a result of the value of R², the 4 independent variables of SL (Organizational Commitment) justified 65% of WA. Hence, 35% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.10. Spiritual Leadership (Productivity) and WA

The relationship between SL (Productivity) and WA is determined. The seventh hypothesis to be tested is:

H7: There is no relationship between SL (Productivity) and WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt

Table (13): MRA Results for SL (Productivity) and WA

The Variables of Productivity	Beta	R	R ²
1. Everyone is busy in my department/grade; there is little idle time.	0.053	0.053	0.002
2. In my department, work quality is a high priority for all employees.	0.844**	0.534	0.294
3. In my department, everyone gives his/her best efforts.	1.09**	0.001	0.001
4. My work group is very productive.	1.10**	0.070	0.004
5. My work group is very efficient in getting maximum, output from the resources (money, people, equipment, etc.) we have available	0.097*	0.126	0.015
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.736 0.542 69.471 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01			

Table (13) proves that there is a relationship between SL (Productivity) and WA. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of SL (Productivity) can explain 54% of the total differentiation in WA level. For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of SL (Productivity) and WA is obtained. Because MCC is 0.74, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9. Research Results

By reviewing the results of descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the research hypothesis, the study reached a set of results which will be reviewed and discussed as follows:

1. The availability of some administrative factors that cause WA such as the lack of welcome of the senior management of the organization to the idea of Telework, and the failure to recruit employees in the degree of career commensurate with their experience and skills, and the existence of a capacity of competition between the administrative departments of the organization in a manner that causes problems to each other, senior management to criticize and blame the workers, In addition to ignoring some in the promotion movement within the organization. This is in addition to the existence of a set of individual factors that cause WA such as the inability of the individual to achieve a balance between duties and social responsibilities, resulting in a sense of mental fatigue, and delay the performance of some of the tasks to be accomplished. In addition, the employee loses the ability to develop his career. This is reflected in his belief that the introduction of the computer threatens his job stability and that the training courses are a waste of time.
2. The general average of SL at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt is fairly high. The vision as one of the dimensions of SL ranked first, followed by the meaning/calling in the second place, the hope and faith in the third place, the membership in the fourth place, the organizational commitment in the fifth place, the altruistic love ranked sixth, and finally the productivity as one of the dimensions of SL at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

3. The general average of the behavior of development at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt is somewhat low. Behavior was followed by verbal physical development, followed by physical development in second place, physical development versus property in third place, and social WA in fourth place as a dimension of WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.
4. There is a statistically significant inverse correlation between the variable of SL (vision, hope/faith, altruism, meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, productivity) and the variable of WA (lack of incentives for Telework, negative management outlook for employees, increase organizational conflicts, the senior management adopts the method of bullying at work, the inability of the individual to balance the functional and social, loss of ability to develop career) where the greater the interest in SL, the less WA is at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

10. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations. These recommendations can be summarized as follows:

1. The degree of WA varies in terms of their nature and degree of impact on employees at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. It may be an impetus for development and improvement, an opportunity for challenge and self-validation, and may be a source of innovation and the emergence of creative ideas. Therefore, it is important to consider the factors that lead to increased willingness and willingness of the employees to express their ideas and opinions and to enhance their positive attitudes towards the process of innovation and creativity by providing material and moral incentives to motivate them to innovate and innovate.
2. Conduct positive training courses and focus on the need to provide senior management support to staff members in a manner that prevents WA at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. Training courses are a means of building positive skills, abilities and behaviors, not a waste of time.
3. Taking into account the appointment of employees at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt in the appropriate degree of expertise, skills and abilities.
4. Adopting modern administrative methods in work, such as Telework, which ensures the possibility of continuous communication of employees with their organization regardless of their social conditions in different forms.
5. Rehabilitation training courses at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt that support the change of individual factors that cause resistance to change.
6. To confirm the employee's ability to self-development by converting him to the conviction that the introduction of the computer does not threaten his career stability, but saves his time, and raises the degree of quality and accuracy of work at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt.

11. Future Research Proposals

The current research sought to reveal the role of SL in controlling the behavior of development at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt. However, the scope of this research and the methods used in the results and indicate the existence of areas for future studies that are no less important in this regard. These include: (1) the role of SL in reducing workplace bullying; (2) quality of work life as an approach to control WA; and (3) evaluation of WA in Egyptian universities, (4) role stress and WA, and (5) workplace bullying and WA .

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